

The Effect of Micro Influencer (Source Trustworthiness, Source Expertise, Source Attractiveness, Message Authenticity, Message Believability) on Online Purchase Intention for Makarizo Product

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Abstract:- This study explores the relationship between source trustworthiness, source expertise, source attractiveness, message authenticity, and message believability towards the online purchase intention of Makarizo products in the realm of micro influencers. The results of the research show that source trustworthiness and message authenticity have a positive and significant effect on online purchase intention, while source attractiveness, source expertise, and message believability do not have a significant effect. These findings provide insights for marketers who use micro influencers as a channel for promoting messages about the antecedents that trigger online purchase intention after the audience is exposed to advertising messages.

Keywords:- *Micro Influencer, Source Trustworthiness, Source Expertise, Source Attractiveness, Message Authenticity, Message Believability.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with the increasing use of social media by society, more and more companies are using social media to conduct marketing activities. However, social media managed by companies tend to lack power [19]. Therefore, companies use social media influencers as communicators to deliver advertising messages, or what is referred to as influencer marketing. Influencer marketing is a marketing strategy that uses opinion leaders on social media, known as social media influencers, as communicators to deliver product or company messages. Influencer marketing has a lower cost compared to conventional advertising (such as TV, billboards, etc.), and is supported by features on social media platforms that facilitate the process of analyzing and evaluating results more transparently.

In the context of influencer marketing, there is some debate regarding the factors that influence the effectiveness of influencer marketing [18] states that the factors that influence purchase intention are social media influencers, message quality, message credibility, and e-wom engagement. This is also in line with research which states that the message

credibility factor has a significant influence on purchase intention [27]. Meanwhile [14] message credibility is significantly influenced by message authenticity, message believability, and message accuracy. Then there is research [15] stating message accuracy, message relevancy, message currency describes message credibility. Although some previous studies have stated several factors that significantly influence the success of influencer marketing in affecting purchase intention, it should be noted that these factors may not necessarily apply in Indonesia, as demographic differences can lead to differences in consumer behavior. In addition, the classification of influencers can also affect which indicators influence the success of influencer marketing. Referring to their number of followers, influencers can be classified into four types [8]: nano influencers, micro influencers, macro influencers, and mega influencers. Nano influencers have fewer than 1,000 followers. Micro influencers have between 1,000 and 100,000 followers. Macro influencers have between 100,000 and 1,000,000 followers. Finally, mega influencers, or often referred to as celebrity influencers, have more than 1,000,000 followers. Recommendations from micro influencers are more preferred as they are more authentic and less famous compared to macro influencers [2]. Several factors possessed by micro influencers such as trustworthiness, attractiveness, competency, and self-representation of the influencer have an impact on purchase intention [16].

This study focuses on identifying the factors that influence the effectiveness of micro-level influencer marketing on online purchase intention. The online purchase intention variable was chosen as the dependent variable because purchase intention is one of the affective effects that consumers feel after being exposed to a marketing message, and the increase in online purchase intention in society can be maximized to increase product sales. One of the effective factors used to create online purchase intention is influencer marketing [17].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Social Learning Theory*

Social learning theory is used as a contextual framework to understand social media influencers as representatives of third-party endorsers, a concept similar to celebrities that can shape audience attitudes on social media for decision making [12]. This theory suggests that an individual's intention to purchase a product is greatly influenced by the attitudes of the respondent and the effectiveness of social media influencers [11].

B. *Influencer Marketing*

Influencer marketing is used as a marketing strategy that utilizes the influence of individuals or key opinion leaders to promote brand awareness or purchasing decisions. In influencer marketing, influencers refer to people who have strong influence and are able to communicate ideas to their followers to accept what is presented online or promote and sell products through their social media. Thus, influencer marketing strategy is a promotion strategy that uses people who have influence in the social media they use. Influencer marketing strategy is a suitable and effective strategy, supported by a more transparent and easy-to-evaluate target market analysis due to the features of social media [21]. Additionally, the cost is lower compared to advertising on television.

C. *Social Media*

Social media has a global reach that is not limited by time and geography. Some of the current social media platforms include Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, Blog Twitter, Tiktok, and others [3]. Based on previous research, social media influencers have a positive impact on consumers' purchase intentions, as their promotions increase purchase intention by 89.7% [13].

D. *Source Trustworthiness*

Influencer credibility is the most important factor for promotional effectiveness [10]. Trustworthiness refers to the ability of the source perceived to be honest, have integrity, and be reliable [23]. Trusted influencers can influence audiences even if they have ordinary abilities. This is in line with research showing that influencers with high levels of trustworthiness are known as individuals who provide consistent and reliable information and deliver as promised [9].

E. *Source Expertise*

Expertise shows that a source has knowledge about the advertised product, and this knowledge is based on experience. Research shows that source expertise in persuasive communication generally indicates that the source has a positive impact on behavior change. Source expertise also indicates how far the target audience is engaged in the message content [26].

Expertise is also considered a skill where a communicator can provide valid statements and refer to the knowledge, experience, skills, and expertise of the endorser [1]. Expertise is also related to the endorsed products. Ohanian states that expertise is felt to be more important in explaining and influencing purchase intention than other components.

F. *Source Attractiveness*

Attractiveness refers to the visual appeal that targets the sense of sight and the appeal of the source in delivering a message. Although not rational, it is natural for everyone to like a visually appealing appearance. Some studies in the field of advertising and communication suggest that physical attractiveness is an important signal for individual assessments of others. Although there are many studies focused on the construct of physical attractiveness, the issues raised are still not very clear [26].

G. *Message Authenticity*

The concept of authenticity refers to a message that is delivered in an authentic way based on real life and is acceptable to consumers and influences their subsequent behavior, namely purchase intention. This study examines the authenticity of messages delivered by micro-influencers in promoting Makarizo products received from their followers on Instagram.

H. *Message Believability*

The most important indicator of message credibility is the belief and authenticity of the message, especially in messages delivered through online media [14]. To measure the credibility of a message based on belief, questions can be asked to participants. The credibility of a message can be influenced by both the source of the message and non-source factors. Information from the source is very important because it forms the basis for evaluating credibility. Based on the above, it can be concluded that message believability refers to the consumer's perception of how likely and convincing, and how much they trust the message. In this study, message believability is observed through the delivery of messages, either through captions or videos uploaded by micro-influencers in promoting Makarizo products that are received by consumers in influencing their purchase intentions.

I. *Purchase Intention*

The factors that influence consumer purchase intention are the attitudes of others, to what extent the attitudes of others reduce preferred alternatives, and the motivation of consumers to follow the desires of others. Another factor is the situation, which can change the consumer's decision to make a purchase. This will depend on the consumer's own thoughts, whether they believe in the situation and decide to make a purchase or not [7].

J. Framework

Fig 1 Framework

Based on the research problem, theoretical review, and framework, the hypothesis proposed in this study is:

- H1: Micro influencer source trustworthiness has a significant effect on online purchase intention.
- H2: Micro influencer source expertise has a significant effect on online purchase intention.
- H3: Micro influencer source attractiveness has a significant effect on online purchase intention.
- H4: Micro influencer message authenticity has a significant effect on online purchase intention.
- H5: Micro influencer message believability has a significant effect on online purchase intention.

III. METHODOLOGY RESEARCH

A. Research Desgin

This study uses quantitative research method. Quantitative method is a type of research method that involves numerical data that is processed and analyzed using statistical or mathematical calculations [20]. This study also uses hypothesis with a causal associative approach to determine the relationship between two or more variables. The causal associative hypothesis aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables, which indicates a cause-and-effect relationship. Causality design is a scientific approach to research that tests whether one variable causes another variable to change or not.

There are two entities that are the objects of research, namely the company and the micro influencer as the source of marketing messages. The research object chosen to represent the company is Makarizo, with the following reasons: Makarizo is one of the companies that actively uses influencer marketing, Makarizo received an award in 2017-2022 as the second position in the top brand index in the personal care category and hair spray sub-category [24]. Makarizo is one of the companies engaged in the hair care industry, in which the hair care industry has the second largest market share in the cosmetics market in Indonesia, accounting for 23% in 2019 [22]. Regarding Makarizo, the researcher specifically focuses on Makarizo Hair Energy Scentration as the newest product released among other Makarizo products. The research object representing the micro influencer is Clarissa Sabrina. Clarissa Sabrina was chosen as the micro influencer/subject of this study because Clarissa with her Instagram account @clarsabb is an influencer who has 6512 followers as of October 2022 in the beauty care field, where Makarizo is also present in a relevant field. Based on observation, Clarissa Sabrina is also an active micro influencer who makes at least one post per week.

Table 1 Research Desgin

No	VARIABEL	INDIKATOR
1	Purchase Intention (Wilopo, 2021)	1. Audience is interested in buying the product after seeing the product review. 2. Audience will give product recommendations after seeing product reviews 3. Audience is interested in making the reviewed product the first choice of product compared to competitors 4. Audience is interested in finding new information about the product after seeing the product review
2	Source Trustworthiness (Wilopo, 2021)	1. Micro influencer is honest in providing information about products. 2. Micro influencer can be trusted as a source of reference for followers to influence them to buy products. 3. Micro influencer is a person that followers can trust by looking at the advertisements made for the product
3	Source Expertise (Niftah & Rahmat, 2017)	1. Micro influencer has good knowledge of Makarizo products 2. Micro Influencers have a good backgrounds
4	Source Attractiveness (Niftah & Rahmat, 2017)	1. Micro influencer has physical appeal in promoting Makarizo products. 2. Micro influencer has the ability communication in delivering the message.
5	Message Authenticity (Shoenberger et al., 2020)	1. The message that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on Instagram micro influencers is an authentic message. 2. The message that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on

		Instagram micro influencers is in accordance with reality. 3. The message that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on Instagram micro influencers is made as it is.
6	Message Believability (Krakow et al., 2018)	1. The message that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on Instagram micro influencers can be trusted. 2. Messages that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on Instagram micro influencers have information expected by the audience 3. Message that delivered in the promotion of Makarizo products on Instagram micro influencers have a consistent pattern

B. Data Collection Methods

The source of this research is primary data obtained from respondents who have agreed to fill out the questionnaire. Primary data refers to information obtained directly by researchers regarding the variables of interest for the specific purpose of the research [6]. The data collection method used in this study was a survey using a questionnaire via Google Form to obtain data on the respondents' identity and understanding.

C. Population and Sample

The population used in this study is the followers of micro influencer Clarissa Sabrina, which is 6512 followers as of October 2022. For the value of e in the Slovin formula, the following conditions apply: • e value = 0.1 (10%) for large populations • e value = 0.2 (20%) for small populations. In this study, a value of e = 0.1 or 10% is used. The sample size calculated using the formula in this study is 98.48 = 99 respondents. The number of 99 respondents meets the minimum criteria for the required number of respondents in this study. However, to provide better data for this study, 136 respondents were used, who are active Instagram users, followers of Clarissa Sabrina, and have seen the product review posts of Makarizo on the Instagram account of the micro influencer Clarissa Sabrina.

D. Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method used in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). SEM is a multivariate technique used to describe a model concept with variables that cannot be directly measured, but can be measured through their indicators [24]. Partial Least Squares (PLS) is a component-based or variance-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model. PLS SEM can explain measurement errors and also present moderation effect calculations more accurately.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaires, resulting in 136 responses from respondents. It is known that out of the 136 respondents, 78 (57%) were female and 58 (43%) were male. In terms of age, 118 (86.8%) of the respondents were aged between 21-30 years old, 17 (12.5%) were aged between 31-40 years old, and 1 (0.7%) respondent was over 40 years old.

A. Descriptive Analysis

➤ **Purchase Intention**

The indicator of the Purchase Intention variable that has the highest average of 3.92 is Indicator Y1.1, namely "Audience is

interested in buying Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation products after seeing reviews of these products on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram". Meanwhile, indicator Y1.3, "Audience is interested in making Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation the first choice of hair fragrance products after seeing the product review on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram" is the indicator that has the lowest average of 3.43 of Purchase Intention.

➤ **Source Trustworthiness**

The indicator of the Source Trustworthiness variable that has the highest average of 3.93 is X1.1, namely "Clarissa Sabrina has honesty in the Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation review". While Indicator X1.3 "Clarissa Sabrina can be relied on as a source of reference for buying Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation products" has an average of 3.75 from the Source Trustworthiness variable.

➤ **Source Expertise**

The indicator of the Source Expertise variable that has the highest average of 3.96 is Indicator X2.2, namely "Clarissa Sabrina has a good background ..". While the indicator that has the lowest value is indicator X2.1 "Clarissa Sabrina has good knowledge about Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation" has an average of 3.92 from the Source Expertise variable.

➤ **Source Attractiveness**

The indicator of the Purchase Intention variable that has the highest average of 4.42 is Indicator X3.1, namely "Clarissa Sabrina has physical attractiveness in promoting Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation". While the indicator that has the lowest value is indicator X3.2 "Clarissa Sabrina has communication skills in delivering messages." has an average of 4.34 in the variable Source Attractiveness of Makarizo products.

➤ **Message Authenticity**

The indicators of the Message Authenticity variable that have the highest average of 3.97 are Indicators X4.1 and X4.3, namely "The message delivered in the Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation review on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram is an authentic message." For X4.1 and "The message delivered in the Makarizo review on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram is made as it is (honest)." While the indicator that has the lowest score is indicator X4.2 "The message delivered in the Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation review on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram is a message that is in accordance with reality." has an average of 3.92 in the Message Authenticity variable.

➤ **Message Believability**

The indicator of the Message Believability variable that has the highest average of 4.33 is Indicator X5.2, namely "The message delivered in the Makarizo product review on Clarissa

Sabrina's Instagram has the information expected by the audience." While the indicator that has the lowest value is indicator X5.3 "The message delivered in the Makarizo Hair Energy Scentsation review on Clarissa Sabrina's Instagram is consistent." has an average of 3.90 in the Message Believability variable.

B. Outer Model Testing

➤ *Convergent Validity*

The outer loading value can be seen that all items or indicators have an outer loading value > 0.5. The limitation of the outer loading value > 0.5 is still acceptable as long as the validity and reliability of the construct meet the requirements and the model is still being developed. So based on the validity of outer loading, it is stated that all items or indicators are valid. In this study, the outer loading value for the source trustworthiness variable for indicator X1.1 is 0.851, X1.2 is 0.927, X1.3 is 0.858, then the source expertise variable for indicator X2.1 is 0.892, X2.2 is 0.880, then the source attractiveness variable for X3.1 is 0.902, X3.2 is 0.919, then the message authenticity variable for X3.1 is 0.902, X3.2 is 0.919, then the message authenticity variable for X3.1 is 0.902, X3.2 is 0.919. X4.1 is worth 0.817, X4.2 is worth 0.901, X4.3 is worth 0.939, then the message believability variable X5.1 is worth 0.870, X5.2 is worth 0.871, X5.3 is worth 0.868, and the purchase intent variable indicator Y1 is worth 0.911, Y2 is worth 0.880, Y3 is worth 0.832.

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

The Cross Loading value for all variables of this research model has a value above 0.7. So it can be concluded that Discriminant Validity has met the requirements.

➤ *AVE Testing Result*

All variables in the study are valid, because the AVE value is above the requirement of 0.50. Where source trustworthiness has a value of 0.773, source expertise of 0.785, source attractiveness of 0.829, message authenticity of 0.788, message believability of 0.756 and purchase intention of 0.733.

➤ *Fornell Lacker Criterion*

The root AVE value of each variable is higher than the correlation value between that variable and other variables in the model. For example, the ST variable (X1) AVE root is 0.879 and this value is greater than the correlation of ST with other constructs, namely with SE of 0.739, with SA of 0.810, with MA of 0.758, with MB of 0.758, and with PI of 0.795.

With this, it can be said that according to the test with the AVE root, the model has good discriminant validity

➤ *Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability Results*

Composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha shows a satisfactory value, namely the value of each variable above the minimum value of 0.70. Where the source trustworthiness variable has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.853 and composite reliability has a value of 0.911, the source expertise variable has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.727 and composite reliability has a value of 0.880, the source attractiveness variable has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.794 and composite reliability has a value of 0.907, message authenticity has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.863 and composite reliability has a value of 0.917, message believability has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.840 and composite reliability has a value of 0.903, and the purchase intention variable has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.878 and composite reliability has a value of 0.916.

C. Inner Model Testing

➤ *R-square value*

Obtained the R-Square value of the Online Purchase Intention Variable (Y) of 0.707. This R-Square value means that the variability of the Online Purchase Intention construct can be explained by the variability of the ST, SE, SA, MA, and MB constructs by 70.7% while the remaining 29.3% is explained by other variables outside those studied.

➤ *F-square value*

The value of f^2 can be stated that the ST variable on the PI variable produces an f^2 value of 0.192, so the effect is classified as moderate. The SE variable on the PI variable produces an f^2 value of 0.018, so its effect is classified as moderate. The SA variable on the PI variable produces an f^2 value of 0.005, so the effect is classified as low. The MA variable on the PI variable produces an f^2 value of 0.160, so its effect is classified as moderate. While the MB variable on the PI variable f^2 value of 0.004, the effect is classified as low.

➤ *Q-square value*

The results of the Cross-validated Redundancy test can be explained that the Q2 value is 0.505. Because the value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

Table 2 Hypothesis Testing

Hipotesis	Original Sample	t- Statistics	P values	Keterangan
H1 Source Trustworthiness → Online Purchase Intention	0,483	5,282	0,000	Positive Significant
H2 Source Expertise → Online Purchase Intention	-0,121	1,420	0,156	Not Significant
H3 Source Attractiveness → Online Purchase Intention	0,070	0,778	0,437	Not Significant
H4 Message Authenticity → Online Purchase Intention	0,390	4,913	0,000	Positive Significant
H5 Message Believability → Online Purchase Intention	0,064	0,809	0,419	Not Significant

The influence between variables is declared significant if it has a t-statistic value greater than 1.96 or has a P value <0.05. There are 2 variables that have significant results, namely source trustworthiness and message authenticity.

D. Analysis of Results

➤ Source Trustworthiness

As an actor whose role is to add value to a brand, product, or service, trustworthy influencers are predicted to be able to influence audiences despite their mediocre abilities. The source trustworthiness variable is divided into three indicators, namely honesty, reliability, and trustworthiness. Based on the research results, source trustworthiness in micro influencers has a significant effect on online purchase intention with a t-statistics value of 5.282 or greater than 1.96 and P values of 0.000 or less than 0.05. Thus, the first hypothesis which states that source trustworthiness has a significant effect on online purchase intention is proven and can be stated as accepted. Several previous studies have confirmed how source trustworthiness affects online purchase intention. However, there is no research that specifically examines how the fake engagement phenomenon affects source credibility, especially trustworthiness. We assume that the emergence of the fake engagement phenomenon followed by audience awareness of the phenomenon is one of the antecedents that cause source trustworthiness to be the only message source-based variable in this study that has a significant effect on online purchase intention. If the audience is able to perceive the micro influencer as a trustworthy, honest, and reliable source of messages as a source of online purchase intention, then the micro influencer will have a significant effect on online purchase intention.

➤ Source Expertise

Source expertise refers to how the audience perceives the source of the message as a person who has knowledge of the advertised product because they have experience on relevant topics. This variable is divided into two indicators, namely the micro influencer's background and the micro influencer's knowledge of the product. The results showed that the source expertise variable has no effect on online purchase intention because it has a t-statistics value of 1.420 or smaller than 1.96 and P values of 0.156 or greater than 0.05. When referring to the results of research by [8] which states that source expertise has a significant effect on consumer purchase intention at the celebrity endorsement level, the concept of source expertise in micro influencer practices has no influence on online purchase intention.

➤ Source Attractiveness

Source attractiveness refers to the level of attractiveness of a message source, including physical attractiveness and communication skills. The results showed that the source attractiveness variable has a t-statistics value of 0.778 or smaller than 1.96 and P values of 0.437 or greater than 0.05. Thus the third hypothesis which states that source attractiveness has a significant effect on online purchase intention on Makarizo products can be stated as not accepted. If we dissect the concept of social media influencers definitively, social media influencers are ordinary social

media users who create their own persona by raising certain topics such as beauty, fashion, and so on. These topics then create a pool of audience with similar topics of interest organically. At the micro influencer level, the relationship that occurs between micro influencers and their audience is intimate given the relatively small audience. Researchers assume that in the context of micro influencers, the influence of source attractiveness variables on brands is only at the cognitive level (awareness), or means that source attractiveness does not affect audience attitudes (purchase intention) towards brands. This is supported by research which states that in mega influencers, source attractiveness affects source trustworthiness and source expertise, but does not have a direct influence on audience attitudes towards brands [5].

➤ Message Authenticity

The message authenticity variable is divided into three indicators, namely authentic messages, realistic messages, and honest messages. Based on the research results, it is known that message authenticity on micro influencers has a positive effect on online purchase intention. This is because t-statistics has a value of 4.913 which means greater than 1.96 and P values of 0.000 or less than 0.05. The results of the study which show that message authenticity has a significant effect on online purchase intention can be supported by the persuasion knowledge model. Generation Z and millennials who are "native users" of social media have been exposed to many advertising messages and have the awareness to distinguish commercial messages from non-commercial messages [4]. This is consistent with the data findings in this study, which show that the majority of the audience for Makarizo's influencer marketing messages are dominated by generation Z and millennials, aged 21-30 years. Furthermore, when generation Z realizes that an uploaded content is an advertising message or a persuasive message, they will tend to refuse to be persuaded [4]. Thus, the authenticity of advertising messages uploaded by micro influencers is one of the important factors that influence online purchase intention.

➤ Message Believability

Based on the results of the study, it is known that the message believability of micro influencers has no effect on online purchase intention. This is based on the t-statistics value which is smaller than 1.96, which is 0.809, and P values of 0.419 or greater than 0.05. Thus, the fifth hypothesis which states that micro influencer message believability has a positive effect on online purchase intention is not accepted. This is supported by a study which states that the message believability of micro influencers does not have a significant influence on purchase intention in the context of skincare advertising messages. This study found that perceived similarity between micro influencers and followers has a greater influence than message believability in influencing purchase intention [25].

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion in study of "The Influence of Micro Influencers (Source Trustworthiness, Source Expertise, Source Attractiveness, Message Authenticity, Message Believability) on Online Purchase Intention of Makarizo Products", the following conclusions :

- *Source Trustworthiness* has a significant effect on *Online Purchase Intention*.
- *Source Expertise* has no significant effect on *Online Purchase Intention*.
- *Source Attractiveness* has no significant effect on *Online Purchase Intention*.
- *Message Authenticity* has a significant effect on *Online Purchase Intention*.
- *Message Believability* has no significant effect on *Online Purchase Intention*.

Recommendations for future research to use a larger sample size and by adjusting the *micro influencer's* follower *insights*, and explore how the influence of source expertise on micro influencers on online purchase intention on products that are specialized and unfamiliar, and how the influence of source attractiveness on online purchase intention micro influencers on influencer marketing effectiveness at the cognitive level.

For companies, it is recommended to curate micro influencers not only based on the relevance of the product to the topic carried by the micro influencer, but companies need to consider the relevance between the company's target market and the target audience of the micro influencer. Meanwhile, it is also necessary to consider the intensity of micro influencers in uploading advertising content to enable influencer marketing activities to be effective. In addition, to enable micro influencers to upload authentic and interactive messages, companies need to give micro influencers limited freedom in reviewing products and not only focus on product benefits.

For micro influencers, that should be consistent in improving their credibility as a source of messages and the ability to communicate advertising messages. Some things that can be recommended by researchers include micro influencers need to pay attention to the comparison of the quantity of advertising content with the quantity of personal content. The quantity of advertising content should be less when compared to personal content, micro influencers need to communicate advertising messages by placing themselves as an audience or as consumers of the advertised product, there needs to be a description of paid sponsorship if the uploaded content is advertising content.

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